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INNOVATIONS IN BUILDING TECHNOLOGIES FOR HABITABLE HOUSING ON THE MOON USING LOCAL LUNAR RESOURCES AS BUILDING MATERIALS

Abstract

The article discusses the creation of a habitable dwelling on the Moon, suitable for a long-term mission of Earthlings on the Moon for research, work and comfortable living. The implementation of an inhabited dwelling with the maximum use of lunar resources and the possibilities of near space is proposed. In particular, solutions are given for energy supply by creating an "eternal day" in certain places by placing mirrors at Lagrange points in the Earth-Moon system, and original solutions for electrical and heat supply of a dwelling based on direct conversion of solar radiation and electrization of regolith, the design of an inhabited module with low heat loss, a heat supply system based on direct conversion of solar energy into thermal energy and the use of a heat accumulator, the use of 3D printing technology.

Keywords: Habitable dwelling, lunar resources, "eternal day", Lagrange points, solar radiation, electrization of regolith, heat accumulator.

1. Introduction.

The exploration of the Moon by spacecraft began on January 2, 1959, with the launch of the Soviet automatic interplanetary station Luna-1 on a flight path to the Moon. In the future, the study of the moon continued both with the help of descent vehicles and manned expeditions of American astronauts. Samples of lunar soil were delivered and studied from the surface of the Moon [1].

After flying around the moon and landing on its surface, the chief designer of the Soviet space exploration program S.P. Korolev considered it expedient to create a permanent lunar base: "The organization on the Moon of a permanent scientific station, and subsequently an industrial facility, will make it possible to use those untouched and still unknown a celestial body close to us for science and the national economy [1].

In May 2024, a manned flyby of the Moon is planned in the Artemis 2 mission. In 2025, people are planned to land on the lunar surface in the Artemis 3 mission. Luna-26 is a Russian orbital mission to the Moon, scheduled for November 13, 2024. Luna-27 is a Russian landing mission to the Moon, planned for 2025. Luna-28 is a Russian landing mission to the Moon, planned for 2027. Luna-29 is a Russian landing mission to the Moon, planned for 2028. China also makes no secret of plans to establish an international scientific base at the south pole of the moon. The implementation of this project is scheduled for the first half of the 2030s [2].

The flight and subsequent colonization of the Moon is unlikely to bring economic benefits in the near future. Even the extraction of helium-3 is rather a plan. But it is necessary to fly, because the orbital station and the settlement of the satellite are important marks in the history of science and mankind, which can become a starting point for future space expansion.

The purpose of the article is to give impetus to the development of technologies necessary for the mission. "In order to explore other worlds, we need new and innovative technologies adapted to these environments and our exploration needs," says Nicky Werkheiser, director of technology development at NASA's Office of Space Technology (STMD). "Promoting this development with our commercial partners will create the capabilities we need for future missions."

To date, the geography of the Moon, temperature conditions, the flux and spectral characteristics of solar radiation on the satellite surface, and the properties of the lunar soil are largely known, which can become a good basis for designing a habitable module on the surface of the planet. Table 1 presents the main data on the conditions on the surface of the Moon [3].

Table 1 presents basic data on the conditions on the lunar surface.

Ambient pressure	10^{-10} mm Hg
Gravity	1/6 g
Temperature range	$\pm 150^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 440 BTU/h solar energy flow
Electromagnetic radiation	Intense infrared and ultraviolet radiation, as well as in the visible range

A day on one side of the Moon lasts about 13.5 days, and the next 13.5 days it is plunged into darkness.

The temperature conditions on the Moon are as follows [3]:

- When sunlight hits the moon's surface, temperatures can reach 127°C . After sunset, it can drop to minus 173°C . The temperature changes across the entire surface of the Moon as it rotates both around the Earth and around its own axis.
- However, there are places at the lunar poles that never see daylight. The *Diviner* instrument on the NASA *LRO* probe determined that the temperature in the craters at the south pole of the moon is minus 238°C and minus 247°C in the crater at the north pole.
- The temperature of lunar rocks lying at a depth of 1 m is constant and equal to -35°C .

In 2009, the Japanese *Kaguya* probe discovered a hole in the lunar surface, located near the Marius Hills volcanic plateau, presumably leading to a tunnel below the surface. The diameter of the hole is about 65 meters, and the depth, presumably, is 80 meters [4].

Scientists believe that such tunnels are not single objects on the Moon. They are formed by the solidification of molten rock flows, where lava solidified in the center. These processes occurred during the period of volcanic activity on the Moon. Confirmation of this theory is the presence of sinuous grooves on the surface of the satellite. Such tunnels can serve for colonization, due to protection from solar radiation and the isolation of space, in which it is easier to maintain life support conditions.

2. Research and Methodology. Creating a residential module on the lunar surface

The creation of a residential module on the lunar surface will require solving many technical problems.

2.1. Construction of the residential module.

Until now, human life support systems in space have been created in the conditions of spacecraft and space stations. The manufacture of spacecraft to the last nut was carried out on Earth. The necessary food was also delivered from planet Earth.

When creating a habitable module on the Moon, it is necessary to focus on the maximum possible use of local resources, especially water. The design of the module should include the ability to use local materials and be designed for minimal energy consumption during its operation.

Due to significant difficulties in delivering building materials to the Moon, the subject of study was the use of lunar soil (regolith) for the construction of a habitable module [5-7].

To this end, it is proposed to use 3D printing using lunar soil (regolith) - stones and dust that make up the surface of the Moon - to create a structure that meets the technical and technological requirements for strength [5-7]. When performing construction work, the use of a robotic manipulator is expected. The robotic arm will collect soil for loading into the heliolithograph and move ready-

made stone parts. And the printer will sinter the regolith layer by layer with reflected and focused sunlight.

On the Moon, there are no such influences on the structure of a building as an atmosphere that creates a wind load, seasonal climatic changes characteristic of Earth conditions. Under the conditions of the Moon, one should keep in mind significant diurnal temperature changes, radiative forcing and micrometeorites, which place different requirements on the building structure. With the help of a 3D printer, only the load-bearing shell of the building can be created, the rest of the impacts on the building structure and the microclimate of the residential area must be compensated by other means. The outer shell of the building, in addition to the bearing capacity, must solve problems associated with the noted features: protection from temperature extremes, from vacuum, from radiation exposure. Architectural solutions that allow building on the satellite itself are as important as shuttles and launch vehicles.

2.2 Water supply and air supply.

The solution of the problems of water and oxygen supply depends on the availability of water available on the Moon. Initial supplies of oxygen and water can be brought in from Earth. Water and air recovery and reuse systems must be used to the maximum extent possible, and the inevitable losses must be replenished from local resources. Water and air regeneration systems have been developed and used on spacecraft. Therefore, this issue is not the subject of research in the article. Significant reserves of water have been found on the Moon [8], which can be used in life systems, to create a heat accumulator, and also to extract oxygen by electrolysis.

- The necessary supply of food must be delivered from Earth. In the future, it is possible to create a small autonomous greenhouse, completely autonomous, with artificial lighting and the use of feces as fertilizer.

2.3 Energy supply

One of the key issues in creating a habitable mission on the Moon is energy supply. Based on the results of studying the literature, most researchers propose to use the required number of nuclear power units to provide electricity to lunar settlements, which, in our opinion, is inappropriate due to the significant amount of available solar energy [9].

The flux of solar radiation on the Moon in the daytime is about 1360 W/m² [9], at night it drops to almost zero. The daily cycle of energy intake sets the task of its transformation to a form convenient for use, as well as its accumulation. Most often, in matters of energy supply on the Moon, they consider the conversion of solar energy into electrical energy using photovoltaic cells, which is fully justified by the high level of solar radiation [10–11]. In [11], to ensure a continuous supply of energy without the use of batteries, it is proposed to create a ring of photovoltaic cells near the pole of the planet. In [12], it is proposed to manufacture photovoltaic modules directly from regolith.

We propose the maximum use of solar radiation in the power supply system based on the use of the effect of electrization of lunar dust and the creation of a potential difference with the connection of the payload.

It is advisable to solve the heat supply of the dwelling using the direct conversion of solar energy into thermal energy and the use of a heat accumulator, the energy reserve in which will be sufficient for heat supply during a lunar day, which is about 70 days on Earth. The volume of the heat accumulator will depend on heat losses through the enclosing structures of the dwelling and the volume of hot water consumption. The design of the battery should minimize its heat loss at night. Since the delivery of resources to the Moon is quite problematic, when designing a residential module, it is necessary to provide for the full use of secondary energy resources in the dwelling. In the future, requirements will be developed and the design of a heat accumulator, as well as technical solutions for heating and energy transfer from the accumulator, will be proposed.

An alternative solution that is not found in known literary sources could be the creation of an "eternal day" in the area of the surface adjacent to the habitable module, or better for the entire surface of the Moon. To do this, it is necessary to launch a system of mirrors that direct the flow of solar radiation to the specified area. The dimensions of the mirrors, the requirements for their geometry, the number and location in orbit, the technology of delivery and deployment can be calculated with an appropriate formulation of the problem.

It is possible to manufacture them from a metallized film (with aluminum sputtering). Each reflective module will contain a thin polymeric film with a reflective coating, a system for its deployment and an orientation system. The launch of such a system will not require significant energy consumption due to the low specific density of the reflecting surface and can be performed during the delivery of the mission to the Moon. Calculations show that to ensure the temperature of the Moon's surface in the "eternal day" area equal to +20°C, the re-reflected solar energy flux can be 3 times less than the original flux, which is technically achievable. Experience in creating "cosmic mirrors" is available. Projects with the delivery and deployment of a specular reflective film with an area of up to 70 m² into the Earth's orbit, called "Znamya 2" and "Znamya 3", were successfully completed by Roscosmos [13, 14].

Given the absence of an atmosphere, the reflected beam, with a slight loss in intensity caused by diffraction effects, when propagating over long distances, will reach the surface of the Moon. When creating a "Space Mirror" of a significant scale, with an area of several square kilometers, it is necessary to develop requirements for the irregularities of the mirror surface and solve the technical and technological problems of creating a mirror surface with desired properties and deploying it in space with the necessary orientation and preservation of the desired shape. When creating a system, it is necessary to solve several more problems, including the design of a self-expanding mirror element and a system for pointing the beam into a given area of the Moon's surface.

A variant of the minimum number of reflective elements is possible (the number of elements is 1). In this case, a satellite with a mirror must be launched into orbit around the Earth, to the Lagrange point L1 or L2 in the **Earth-Moon** system:

- to the Lagrange point L1 in the inner orbit closer to the Earth in case the mission is located on the visible side of the Moon;
- to the Lagrange point L2 in an outer orbit higher than the Moon's orbit if the mission is located on the far side of the Moon.

The distance from satellites to the surface of the Moon will be about 60,000 km.

Precision control systems must constantly change the orientation of the mirrors, directing the reflected beam at the location of the lunar mission.

It is possible that a system of two or more satellites will be needed to provide uniform and constant illumination during the lunar night.

Such a solution will reduce the requirements for the capacity of the thermal accumulator and eliminate the need for the accumulation of a significant amount of electrical energy. Over time, it will be possible to place a greenhouse (greenhouse) with a transparent dome in the illuminated area, without the need for additional insulation, as an oasis for growing vegetables and fruits. The pressure inside the dome is at the minimum level necessary for the life of plants. The round-the-clock supply of solar energy will provide the necessary temperature level and conditions for plant photosynthesis. The high ground temperature near the dome minimizes heat loss from the dome.

An additional advantage of creating an "eternal day" zone is to simplify the design of the suit, which will be designed to stay in a vacuum and operate in a range of positive temperatures.

2.4. Production of electric energy

On the moon, it will also be necessary to produce the electrical energy necessary for living on its surface. Currently, it is argued that this can only be done in two ways: converting sunlight into electricity using solar panels and using nuclear fission microreactors.

For example, Blue Origin, using the technology of converting sunlight into electricity, has demonstrated how lunar regolith will become a universal and important material for research [12]. The Blue Alchemist system works by first producing simulated regolith, as there is currently not enough lunar soil on Earth to "invest" in these tests.

Blue Origin's simulated regolith was obtained by paying attention to chemical and mineral variability that varies depending on the lunar zone in which it was collected. This ensures maximum realism of the source material and therefore maximum reliability of the technology for scaling in real conditions on the Moon.

The Blue Alchemist reactor first melts the regolith and then subject it to electrolysis, that is, passing current through the molten material, at temperatures above 1600°C. Through this operation and Blue Origin's patented reactor geometry, iron is extracted first, then silicon, and finally aluminum.

There are a number of influences on the lunar regolith: solar wind streams, solar ultraviolet, micrometeorite streams, plasma of the Earth's magnetotail, and others. Including due to exposure to solar ultraviolet, dust particles in the composition of regolith acquire an electric potential - in other words, they become electrified. Partly for this reason, under certain conditions, dust can begin to break away from the surface and levitate above the surface of the moon. American astronauts noted that dust was one of the major problems they faced on the Moon. She stuck to spacesuits, spacecraft, equipment.

We propose to use the electrization of lunar dust for the production of electrical energy. The proposed technology has a number of advantages compared to the conventional methods mentioned above.

The essence of the scientific idea underlying the proposed design of the power supply system on the Moon is to use the effect of electrization of lunar dust and obtain a potential difference between a fine metal mesh stretched over the surface of the Moon with a thin layer of dust and, at the same time, acquiring the potential of charged dust on the surface (anode), and a metal plate located at a depth of 30-70 m (cathode) with a load connected between them (energy consumers), which provides the necessary power supply. The power supply parameters depend on the degree of dust electrification, the area covered with the grid (cathode dimensions), anode dimensions and other parameters.

The creation of an "eternal day" region can be used to maintain the electrification level of lunar dust in said region. Additionally, electricity generation can be carried out using a mini thermal power plant with focusing elements.

Considering that the level of radiation on the Moon is 200 times higher than the earth's level [1,15], a long-term stay of a person on the Moon is possible only in a space protected from radiation.

Therefore, to implement the idea, it would be advisable to use caves, similar to the holes in the surface of the Moon discovered in 2009 by the Japanese Kaguya probe, located near the Marius Hills volcanic plateau, presumably leading to a tunnel under the surface. The diameter of the hole is about 65 meters, and the depth, presumably, is 80 meters [4].

It can be assumed that such tunnels are not single objects on the Moon. They are formed by the solidification of molten rock flows, where lava solidified in the center. These processes occurred during the period of volcanic activity on the Moon. Confirmation of this theory is the presence of sinuous grooves on the surface of the satellite. Such tunnels can serve for colonization, due to protection from solar radiation and the isolation of the space in which it is easier to maintain life support conditions, as well as to protect part of the proposed device from external influences.

3. Design of the lunar module

The design of the lunar module can consist of an inner shell capable of withstanding the pressure of the atmosphere inside the module and an outer shell that provides the necessary thermal protection and mechanical protection against micrometeorites. Since only radiative heat losses "work" in a vacuum, layered thermal insulation consisting of film layers with reflective sputtering can be effectively used [16]. Additionally, a cavity filled with lunar dust can be used as thermal insulation. The experience of creating powder vacuum thermal insulation [17-19] allows us to consider that the thermal conductivity coefficient of a thermal insulation package filled with lunar dust from regolith can reach a value of the order of $0.001 \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K})$. That is, 10 cm of such thermal insulation will provide a thermal resistance of $100 \text{ m}^2\text{K} / \text{W}$. Of particular interest is the use of such thermal insulation for the part of the module adjacent to the base and the roof.

In combination with the use of reflective thermal insulation layers, the heat loss of the module can be reduced to $1 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$, which for a module with a usable area of 100 m^2 will require a heat source with a power of less than 1 kW for heating and hot water supply. Taking into account the value of the solar constant on the moon, equal to $1360 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$ [9] and the duration of the lunar day, equal to 354 hours, the heat accumulator of the system must give off 354 kWh of thermal energy during the lunar night, which it must store for a lunar day of the same duration. It is enough to ensure the power of thermal energy transferred to the battery equal to 1000 W, which can be solved, taking into account possible heat losses, by creating a thermal solar collector with an area of up to 10 m^2 of sunlit lunar soil.

As a solar collector, it is possible to use pipes with a heat carrier laid in grooves made in dust-free lunar soil, while ensuring good heat transfer from the lunar surface by filling the grooves with a material with high thermal conductivity. When the coolant in the accumulator is heated up to 100°C , the volume of the accumulator should be, taking into account heat losses, about 4 m^3 , i.e., a cube with a side of 1.6 m. Unlike the habitable module, the heat accumulator must be located on an open, sunlit surface. The battery surface area will be 15.4 m^2 . The design of the thermal protection of the thermal accumulator is the same as that of the habitable module. If the heat loss is $10 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$, the energy loss from the battery during the moonlit night will be 40 kWh, i.e., about 5% of the total reserve.

There is no doubt the need to use artificial intelligence (AI) to solve many problems, such as: providing monitoring of the state of processes in residential modules, which will provide a more precise setting of the automation of life support systems, improve the prediction of external conditions and the corresponding state and operation of equipment, which will ensure its more optimal work. Automating systems using AI will significantly increase efficiency and reduce operating costs.

Conclusions

The article is devoted to the creation of a habitable mission on the surface of the Moon with the maximum possible use of local resources for the construction of the module and the use of solar energy to provide it with thermal and electrical energy. To achieve the set goals and solve problems, the following innovative solutions are proposed:

- creation of an "eternal day" zone in the area of the surface adjacent to the residential module by creating and placing mirrors in one of the Lagrange points of the Earth-Moon planetary system, depending on the location of the module, directing the flow of solar radiation to the specified area;
- obtaining electrical energy by creating an electrical circuit between a metal grid that removes an electrical charge from the area of the lunar surface with dust electrically charged by solar radiation, and a rod electrode embedded deep into the lunar surface;
- design of a habitable module with low heat loss, located inside a cavity in the lunar surface and consisting of a sealed inner shell with the ability to withstand the pressure of internal air and an insulated shell based on the use of layered thermal insulation with a high reflection coefficient and thermal insulation material in the form of hollow outer walls filled with lunar dust from regolite;

- a heat supply system based on the direct conversion of solar energy into thermal energy and the use of a thermal accumulator;

- a collector for removing thermal energy from lunar soil in the daytime, made in the form of a pipe with a coolant laid in trenches with a small depth in dust-free lunar soil, ensuring good heat transfer by filling the trenches (furrows) with a material with high thermal conductivity.

To implement the proposed solutions, it is necessary to further develop the design features, calculation methods and manufacturing technologies, delivery to the installation site and deployment of the proposed systems/

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